

Deliverable D15.1

Final Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint

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WP Leaders	Pål Sætrom (NTNU), Miikka Kallberg (CSC)		
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Authors	Pål Sætrom (NTNU) https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8142-7441 Miikka Kallberg (CSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1457-3999 Heikki Lehvälaiho (CSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6263-1356 Stefanie Kirschenmann (CSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2773-4798 Christine Stansberg (UiB) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3665-7843 Haneef Awan (UiO) https://orcid.org/0009-0001-0403-115X Russel Wolff (UiO) Rob Baxter (HDR UK) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3693-8725 Simon Li (UNIVDUN) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7929-2442 Ingeborg Winge (ELIXIR-NO) https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6139-5999 Christian Cole https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2560-2484		

Contributors	
Acknowledgements (not grant participants)	
Reviewers	<p>Elaine Harrison (ELIXIR) https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1149-2242</p> <p>Laia Codó (BSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6797-8746</p> <p>Peter Lényi (MU) https://orcid.org/0009-0009-7840-5458</p>

Log of changes

Date	Mvm	Who	Description
DD/MM/YYYY			

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1. Executive Summary

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability between TREs by development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis – the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework (Blueprint, for short). This document is the third version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Roadmap (Roadmap, for short), presenting a final overview of the steps needed to arrive at the Blueprint that meets requirements from the project use cases, referred to as Drivers, and is viable for TRE providers (referred to as Providers).

The second version of the Roadmap consisted of three phases, with Phases 1 and 2 (in 2024 and 2025) leading to the first and second versions of the Blueprint. The current report summarizes the results of Phase 2, which includes the second version of the Blueprint and accompanying second versions of the training material and machine-readable catalogue of TREs, validation reports from the Drivers and Providers, the second version Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting infrastructure (AAAI) blueprint report with accompanying training material, and second deployable demonstrator report. Furthermore, the report summarizes ongoing developments within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the European Health Data Space (EHDS), and other relevant efforts related to federated analyses of sensitive data within Europe.

Based on the results from Phase 2, we propose continuing with Phase 3 of the Roadmap as planned. Specifically, in Phase 3 (Maturity and Continuity), we will release the final version of the Blueprint. Importantly, Phase 2 has seen a continued high level of engagement and excitement across the project work packages. Building on this momentum, we will continue our planned series of yearly workshops focused on requirements and capabilities (May) and evaluation and adoption (September).

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	Yes
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	Yes
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	Yes
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures	No

<p>framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.</p>	<p>for TREs to support the Five Safes¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)</p>	
	<p>5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	<p>1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	<p>Yes</p>
	<p>2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).</p>	<p>No</p>

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	No
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3. Methods

3.1. Deliverable scope and methodology

The D15.1 deliverable is the final version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Roadmap document (hereafter Roadmap) presenting the steps needed to develop the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint for building an interoperable network of TRE services. This final Roadmap is based on a review of the results from the second phase of the Roadmap and ongoing developments within the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and other relevant efforts related to federated analyses of sensitive data within Europe.

4. Description of work accomplished

The following two sections describe the developments within the second year of the EOSC-ENTRUST project. Internal developments correspond to the second phase in the Updated Roadmap for the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint², while external developments reflect those of related projects relevant for the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. Internal developments include the second versions of the EOSC-ENTRUST Architecture blueprint, Driver validation report, Provider adoption and evaluation report, AAAI report, and Workflows report. External developments include those within the EOSC federation, EHDS, EOSC-ENTRUST's sister projects TITAN and SIESTA, the 1+ Million Genome Initiative (1+MG) and Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI), and Data and Analytics Research Environments UK (DARE-UK).

² Sætrom, P., Kallberg, M., Lehväslaiho, H., Kirschenmann, S., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & van de Sanden, M. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D14.1 Updated Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15608124>

4.1 Summary of EOSC-ENTRUST second year developments

4.1.1 Architecture blueprint

EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable 14.3 (D14.3), Year two version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework³ (hereafter the Blueprint), and its companion Deliverable 14.4 (D14.4), Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year two Blueprint & Interoperability Framework⁴ (hereafter the Training package), were released January 19, 2026. The Blueprint extended the year one version⁵ by providing a revised architecture specification and an updated glossary, initial versions of operating procedures and interface definitions, and analyses of existing and necessary legal agreements in sensitive data federations. The Training package used its foundations from year 1⁶ and the revised Blueprint to provide a draft modular online guide for TRE operators on building, operating, and maintaining federated TREs.

The revised Blueprint architecture was based on a gap analysis and a set of recommendations for the Blueprint⁷, including providing a central access point for user registration, developing a unified data access request procedure, and aligning with ongoing EHDS and EOSC developments. Addressing these recommendations, the revised Blueprint architecture included updated Federation Services for user registration and updated Discovery Service that couples data discovery with data access requests. Importantly, the Discovery Service covers both static metadata catalogues and dynamic cohort discovery and the Blueprint describes additional requirements for such Discovery Services to be EHDS compliant.

The initial Blueprint operating procedures covered User Handling, Data Access and Control, and Federation Governance. These were developed by addressing minimal requirements for sensitive data processing, mapping the Driver user journey and Provider operating procedures to the Blueprint architecture, and then identifying and discussing governance and federation-level operating procedures. The governance and federation-level operating

³ Sætrom, P., Lehväslaiho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., Dijkstra, F., Winge, I., & Hesam, A. (2026). EOSC-ENTRUST D14.3 Year two version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299343>

⁴ Stansberg, C., Awan, H., Wolff, R., & Winge, I. (2026). EOSC-ENTRUST D14.4 Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year two Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299626>

⁵ Sætrom, P., Lehväslaiho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & Hesam, A. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14362388>

⁶ Stansberg, C., & Awan, H. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.2 Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year one Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14361989>

⁷ van der Kant, A., Boiten, J.-W., Rujano, M. A., Ohmann, C., Gonzalo Jimenez, E., Tuikka, A.-M., Wiltshire, D., Casado Barbero, M., Lichtwardt, B., & Bolton, S. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D7.1 Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14988869>

procedures were based on analyses of existing frameworks, primarily the Dataspaces abstraction and the Data Spaces Support Centre⁸.

The initial interface definitions focused on the main components needed for a functional federation, namely the Authentication, Authorization, and Auditing Infrastructure (AAAI; see [Section 4.1.4](#)) and Federation Services interfaces.

The legal agreement analyses described two alternative agreement structures for a TRE federation: peer to peer agreements and consortium agreements. Both structures provide GDPR compliance, but provide different degrees of flexibility and complexity; for example, the peer-to-peer model is more appropriate for transient federations involving a small number of participants. The Blueprint then provides an example consortium agreement and a comparative analysis of existing data processing agreements in use within the Netherlands.

4.1.2 Driver validation report

The deliverable D8.1 - *Driver validation report of Year 2 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis* focuses on a gap analysis of the second EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint document. The Drivers work package held a Gap analysis workshop on December 2-3, 2025 and used this as a base for the report. Different drivers made their own gap analysis and requirements based on the last year version of the Blueprint.

The gap analysis made recommendations for the Final EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, which were grouped under four main topics:

- Architecture Specification
- Standard Operation Procedures (SOP)
- Legal Framework
- Roles and common terminology

The deliverable also recognizes that not all of the Drivers requirements are linked to federation readiness and cannot be added to the Blueprint but probably needs to be addressed in the Requirement Management Framework that is developed by the Provider Forum (WP 11).

4.1.3 Provider adoption and evaluation report

EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable 11.1 (D11.1), Provider adoption and evaluation report of Year 2 blueprint and technology, including barriers to adoption & EOSC readiness of the TRE

⁸ Data Spaces Support Centre, <https://dssc.eu/>

providers with recommendations⁹, was released February 25, 2026. The report describes the updated TRE inventory, the requirements management framework for Driver requirements, the Open TRE Provider Forum, and a Blueprint adoption and EOSC-readiness analysis.

The updated TRE inventory was based on a second survey of TRE providers. Compared to the first survey, the second survey was open to all TRE providers and was therefore broadly disseminated. Moreover, as the TRE inventory forms the basis for the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue (Catalogue)¹⁰, the survey was updated to match the Catalogue structure. The survey was open May–July 2025 and the updated, machine-readable Catalogue was published October 2, 2025. Importantly, the survey and a subsequent gap analysis revealed low levels of federation readiness, diversities in terminology and functionality, fragmented architectures, and low and varying international accessibility.

The requirements management framework was developed to provide a systematic instrument to analyse and verify requirement adoption across heterogeneous TRE providers and federation-level participants. The framework consists of a requirement repository, a requirement adoption traceability matrix, and governance guidance. When applied to the Driver requirements¹¹, the framework helped identify and clarify overlap between requirements, to what extent requirements were verifiable, and the requirements' scope (that is, whether a requirement involved a TRE, the federation, or external actors.)

The Open TRE Provider Forum was launched in April 2025 as a monthly online meeting consisting of news, announcements, and updates, followed by one or two short presentations and ending with a community questions and answers session. As of January 2026, the Open TRE Provider Forum consisted of 42 individuals from 27 TRE service providers.

The Blueprint adoption analysis gathered data from twelve TRE providers. Five of these had either directly adopted or are adapting the Blueprint; the remaining seven were all evaluating or reviewing how the Blueprint aligns with their existing infrastructures. Importantly, the analysis identified several barriers to Blueprint adoption, ranging from technical gaps for shared HPC clusters to emerging questions related to digital sovereignty and financial concerns over the cost of federation. Finally, the report recommends a layered approach to integrating TREs into EOSC, covering policy, governance, and technical levels.

⁹ Vihervalli, U., Azab, A., Zamani, T., Petersen, J. B., van Aalst, S., Hoffmann, N., Codó, L., Iborra de Toledo, P., & Vojacek, L. (2026). EOSC-ENTRUST D11.1 Provider adoption and evaluation report of Year 2 blueprint and technology, including barriers to adoption & EOSC readiness of the TRE providers with recommendations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18769026>

¹⁰ Kallberg, M., & Kirschenmann, S. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D14.2 Machine-readable Second Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17251348>

¹¹ van der Kant, A., Dang, S., Panagiotopoulou, M., Casado Barbero, M., Curwin, A. J., Tuikka, A.-M., Wiltshire, D., Bolton, S., & Lichtwardt, B. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST MS8 Revised Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17376746>

4.1.4 AAI report

During the second year of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, the Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) was formalized through two key elements:

- a training framework supporting pilot deployment, and
- an architectural blueprint for secure handling of sensitive data.

Training and Operational Framework (Deliverable D17.1)¹²

Deliverable D17.1 establishes the foundational training material required for the pilot use of the AAI Trusted Research Environments (TREs). This framework is based on the established Life Science AAI (LS Login)¹³ and allows the project to build on mature, production-level documentation while focusing new content on extensions specific to TREs. The material is structured to support three critical operational roles identified for the pilot phase:

- **TRE Administrators:** Guidance focuses on the technical integration of TRE services, including the registration of OpenID Connect (OIDC) clients and the deployment of Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) using the Open Policy Agent (OPA). The Administrators make sure compliance with security baselines such as Sirtfi v2 and the WISE Baseline Acceptable Use Policy (AUP).
- **TRE Users:** Training covers the complete user lifecycle, emphasizing mandatory identity proofing to record legal identities, the setup of Multi Factor Authentication (MFA), and the linking of digital identities to prevent loss of access.
- **Virtual Organisation (VO) Managers:** Practical instructions are provided for managing the VO lifecycle, defining project-based group structures, and conducting regular audits to ensure the principle of least privilege.

A significant addition in this deliverable is the introductory guidance for the Accounting and Auditing service, which enables the traceability of user actions across the federation.

Architectural Blueprint and Technical Standards (Deliverable D17.2)¹⁴

Deliverable D17.2 presents the second version of the AAI for TREs Blueprint, which serves as the technical blueprint for building an interoperable, secure, and multi-tenant infrastructure. While it adopts the AARC Blueprint Architecture (AARC BPA)¹⁵ as its baseline, it introduces four key enhancements specifically designed to address the unique challenges of handling sensitive data.

- **Secure Account Creation:** Implementation of streamlined procedures for provisioning user identities tailored to the operational context of TREs.

¹² Matyska, L., Lényi, P., Kuba, M., Husgafvel, M., Liampotis, N., Awan, H. (2026). EOSC-ENTRUST Training material for the use of AAI for TREs pilot implementation. Zenodo.

<https://zenodo.org/records/20137207>

¹³ Life Science RI, <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login.html>

¹⁴ Husgafvel, M., Kuba, M., Liampotis, N., Lényi, P., Matyska, L. [D17.2: The AAI for TREs Blueprint, second version](#) [to be published on <https://zenodo.org/communities/eosc-entrust-project/>]

¹⁵ AARC Blueprint Architecture, <https://aarc-community.org/architecture/>

- Rigorous Identity Vetting: Use of high-assurance electronic identification (e.g., eID or eKYC) to verify the authenticity of natural persons across national borders.
- Advanced ABAC Model: A fine-grained authorisation framework that evaluates subject, object, and operation alongside environmental context (e.g., time, location) to centralize and standardize policy decisions.
- Advanced Accounting Layer: An integrated framework for monitoring and tracking usage, designed to answer critical forensic questions (who, what, when, where, and why).

The blueprint further defines a technology-neutral Structured Event Model and the use of a correlation ID (cID) to trace user activity across disparate systems. These technical standards ensure that as the project progresses into its third year, the AAAI can support complex federated analysis use cases while maintaining strict regulatory compliance and security.

4.1.5 Workflows report

EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable 20.1 (D20.1), Second Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows¹⁶, was released on January 19, 2026 along with its companion Deliverable D20.2 Training Package for Digital Objects & Workflows¹⁷. The report describes a prototype that allows federated, provenance-rich, policy-aware analyses across TREs with heterogeneous compute backends. The work includes a Research Object Crate (RO-Crate) validation service, a Five Safes Task Execution Service (TES), and a demonstrator deployed at BSC and UNOTT running a federated workflow for genetic variant calling. In addition to providing several new technical developments, including the RO-Crate validation service and nested container execution, the report demonstrates that the Five Safes TES architecture allows federated workflow execution across TREs. Moreover, the report identifies areas for further improvements, including standards for propagating secrets and deployment considerations for nested containerisation within TREs, which will be further addressed during the project's final year.

¹⁶ Codó, L., Couldridge, J., Chadwick, E., Soiland-Reyes, S., & Mitchell-White, J. (2026). EOSC-ENTRUST D20.1 Second Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299760>

¹⁷ Couldridge, J., & Mitchell-White, J. (2026). EOSC-ENTRUST D20.2 Training Package for Digital Objects & Workflows. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299878>

4.2 External developments

4.2.1 EOSC

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹⁸ is one of the main initiatives contributing to the European strategy for data¹⁹, keeping Europe at the forefront of Open Science by enabling the Web of FAIR data and Services, and supporting the discovery, access and reuse of research outputs within the European Research Area (ERA)²⁰. The evolution of EOSC is guided through the Strategic Research and Innovations Agenda (SRIA) and Multi Annual Roadmaps (MAR)²¹. In the last decade, many organisations within the research and education domain, at national and European level, have contributed to the development of EOSC.

Establishing the EOSC Federation

The deployment of a network between data repositories and services is instrumental for Open Science to progress in Europe. For this, the EOSC Federation of Nodes has been created²². The EOSC Federation will grow to accommodate dozens of EOSC Nodes that are interconnected and can collaborate to share and manage scientific data, knowledge, and resources within and across thematic and geographical research communities. The EOSC Nodes are entry points for users to the EOSC Federation, with each node offering its own and possibly third-party services, including data reposing and accessing services.

The EOSC Federation was officially launched at the EOSC Symposium in November 2025. The transition to an operational federation is planned to happen in 2026 through implementation of the following objectives²³:

- Operational structure: Migrate to the operational structure outlined in the MoU and evolve the federating capabilities and the interoperability framework;
- Transition to production status: Address legal, governance, operational and engagement requirements to move the EOSC Federation from prototype to production status;
- Expansion of the Federation: Enrolment of EOSC Nodes following open calls by the Tripartite Governance as well as onboarding additional resources and use-cases.

¹⁸ EOSC Association, <https://eosc.eu/>

¹⁹ A European strategy for data, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0066>

²⁰ [European Research Area \(ERA\)](#)

²¹ The Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda and its Multi-Annual Roadmap, <https://eosc.eu/sria-mar/>

²² EOSC Federation, <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation>

²³ [EOSC and Research Infrastructures: Opportunities and strategies](#)

The next-wave enrollment call was launched on November 3, 2025 and closed on February 18, 2026. Submitted applications are currently being evaluated, with results expected in April 2026²⁴.

The Federation of Nodes is still in development and some questions remain to be answered. For example:

- How will the EOSC Federation be governed?
- What are the financial mechanisms that will support the resource transactions within the EOSC Federation?

*The EOSC Federation Handbook*²⁵

To support organisations interested in joining the EOSC Federation as a node or to onboard their services, resources, or research output into the federation through an existing federation node, the EOSC Association took the initiative to develop the EOSC Federation Handbook. The EOSC Federation Handbook aims to be a practical guideline for organisations that are interested in making their resources available within and across the EOSC Federation. Last updated in 2026, it has been written through a community-wide collaboration with open consultations, meetings, events and sprints. The handbook details the current governance structure, and the EOSC Node architecture, technical requirements, and services. The document guides stakeholders through the process of making their organisation's digital research resources available to researchers across Europe as part of the EOSC Federation according to the FAIR Guiding Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). It categorises the types of scientific resources that are expected to be made available by an EOSC Node and describes the steps on how to form a Node for organisations wanting to join the EOSC Federation.

EOSC-ENTRUST Network of Trusted Research Environments

Four partners of the EOSC-ENTRUST project (i.e. CSC, ELIXIR, EUDAT, SURF) participate in the build-up phase as members of the first nodes joining the federation. As providing services capable of handling sensitive data has been identified as one of the topics for the build-up phase, EOSC-ENTRUST needs to develop an approach on how TREs are onboarded to the EOSC Federation, for example:

- EOSC-ENTRUST can establish a node offering TRE capabilities and join the EOSC Federation as a node
- The network of TREs can be onboarded to an existing EOSC Node and offer the network of TREs as a service through an EOSC Node

²⁴ EOSC Federation, <https://eosc.eu/news/open-calls-to-grow-the-eosc-federation>

²⁵ EOSC Association. (2026). EOSC Federation Handbook (2.0) [Computer software]. EOSC Association. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999576>

- Organisations offering a TRE can onboard the TRE individually into an EOSC Node of their choice

The EOSC Symposium 2026 will take place from 14 to 16 October in Florence, Italy. As the EOSC flagship event, the Symposium annually brings together the entire stakeholder community, including researchers, policy-makers, organisations and infrastructures to share and celebrate the latest developments around EOSC and the EOSC Federation²⁶. The goal for EOSC-ENTRUST is to present a planned approach of making a Federation of TREs available to the EOSC Federation.

EOSC Post-2027

The negotiations around the EU Partnership landscape for the Union's next framework programme (Horizon Europe 2028-2034), or FP10, have begun and are signaling change. To better prepare for FP10 and to better understand the roles, expectations, and perspectives of its membership, EOSC-A organised a series of consultations in February and March 2026 with Members and Observers to establish a common position on the future of EOSC post-2027²⁷. Members will vote on the adoption of a position paper outlining the preferred governance and funding model for EOSC post-2027 during GA #13 to be held 28-29 May 2026. The primary reasoning behind the position paper is the fact that the European Open Science Cloud is a major initiative of the EU's research and digital agendas that aims to transform Europe's research data ecosystem towards a trusted, secure and sovereign common space of high-quality, FAIR research data and related services.²⁸ It is anticipated the outcome of EOSC post-2027 will have a direct impact on the sustainability of the Blueprint and other EOSC-ENTRUST deliverables; however, at the time of writing, it is difficult to predict to what extent these impacts may be.

4.2.2 EHDS

The European Health Data Space Regulation (EHDS)²⁹ entered into force on March 5, 2026. Currently, we are in the transition period during which the Commission is preparing and finalising implementing acts. For secondary use serving the research community, these start from implementing acts on governance structure, metadata format for datasets available for secondary use, and Secure Processing Environment (SPE). They will apply for electronic health records (EHR) from March 2029 and for other data types two years later. Aligning the Blueprint with EHDS is critical, as EHDS will directly affect research based on

²⁶ EOSC Symposium 2026, <https://eosc.eu/events/eosc-symposium-2026>

²⁷ EOSC, <https://eosc.eu/news/register-for-eosc-a-membership-consultations-on-eosc-post-2027>

²⁸ EOSC and FP10, <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/eosc-and-fp10>

²⁹ EHDS regulation, https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space-regulation-ehds_en

sensitive electronic health data, and will likely have an outsized influence on other areas of sensitive data research.

Preparatory work for EHDS implementing acts has been advised by Second Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space – TEHDAS2³⁰. This project will continue producing outcomes until April 2027.

The key component of EHDS is the SPE, which will be obligatory for secondary use processing of all sensitive data under EHDS. Several activities are currently ongoing to define requirements for SPEs under EHDS, both on European and national levels.

The TEHDAS2 report³¹ (final release expected to be imminent) on SPE recommends a high-level, functional regulation that should not prevent development of new implementing approaches. Being the first international regulation giving precise requirements on sensitive data protection, EHDS will have a huge knock-on effect on all research dealing with any kind of sensitive data. At the same time, EHDS deals mainly with organisational issues involving metadata, discoverability, and data use decision making leaving the data management and interoperability of data services to member states without the clear guidance that should be part of a true EU data space. These guidelines have recently been published by the Data Spaces Support Centre³².

Further, the project «Compliance checks for HealthData@EU and SPEs in the EHDS» is tasked by the EC Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety to Fraunhofer Institute ISST and Ernst & Young to specify the concrete technical requirements on how to process secondary health data within the upcoming EHDS and SPE regulations, and to develop a compliance framework for SPEs within the HealthData@EU Infrastructure. The project group conducted a series of interviews with existing SPE operators and other stakeholders across Europe during winter 2025-26. Based on these interviews and relevant documents, such as the above mentioned TEHDAS2 report, the group proposed a first version of a Requirements Catalogue for SPEs³³, which was reviewed in two workshops during February-March 2026, with invited participants from the earlier interviews. This catalogue is now under further revision. Once the EHDS Regulation will fully enter into force, it is planned that this framework will support compliance activities related to the secondary use of health data.

³⁰ TEHDAS, <https://tehdas.eu/>

³¹ M7.4 Draft technical, functional and security specifications of Secure Processing Environments, <https://tehdas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/draft-technical-functional-and-security-specifications-of-secure-processing-environments.pdf>

³² Data Spaces Support Center Blueprint <https://toolbox.dssc.eu/>

³³ Requirements Catalogue for SPEs – Initial Version [January 2026]

The EOSC-A Health Data Task Force

The EOSC Association Health Data Task force³⁴ aims to shape the EOSC strategy on how to engage with the health data ecosystem and to harmonise and cultivate synergies between EOSC and EHDS. Whereas the Task force's work is still ongoing, their first report identified both gaps and synergies and opportunities related to EHDS's SPEs and existing and ongoing technology developments³⁵.

On SPEs the following gaps have been identified:

- Final requirements specifying the EHDS SPEs are only expected in March 2027. One may therefore see a fragmentation of concepts among institutions.
- Governance and operational clarity of systems are still uncertain. It is therefore unclear for service developers where and how they can integrate their services, which can lead to a growing landscape of fragmented concepts and platforms.
- Federated analysis is a principle under EHDS, but there is no operationalisation yet.

Similarly, the following synergies and opportunities were identified:

- The EHDS should leverage existing infrastructure within EOSC
- EHDS and EOSC should align their requirements and certification
- EHDS and EOSC should build mutually interoperable European catalogues
- EOSC infrastructures should pilot EHDS compliance
- EHDS should harness the emerging AI opportunities within EOSC

4.2.3 EOSC-TITAN and EOSC-SIESTA

The joint workshop between EOSC-ENTRUST, EOSC-TITAN³⁶ and EOSC-SIESTA³⁷ was held on December 10, 2025³⁸.

The aim for the workshop was to share information of the projects' goals and status between these sister projects.

Based on the workshop presentations and discussions it became clear that EOSC-TITAN and EOSC-SIESTA are more focused on the technical details of TRE environments whereas EOSC-ENTRUST is trying to provide a more high-level approach of building the trust between TRE environments.

³⁴ EOSC-A Health Data Task Force <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/health-data-task-force>

³⁵ EOSC Health Data Task Force. Deliverable 1 <https://zenodo.org/records/19254262>

³⁶ EOSC Titan, <https://titan-eosc.eu/>

³⁷ EOSC-SIESTA, <https://eosc.eu/eu-project/siesta/>

³⁸ EOSC SIESTA, ENTRUST and TITAN joint workshop, <https://indico.ifca.es/event/3549/>

4.2.4 Other initiatives

4.2.4.1 1+MG/GDI

The Genomic Data Infrastructure³⁹, launched in November 2022, brings together over 70 institutes across 24 European countries and two international organisations to implement the vision of the 1+ Million Genomes Initiative⁴⁰. Its mission is to enable secure, cross-border access to genomic, phenotypic, and clinical data to advance research, policymaking, and healthcare in Europe. Building on the outputs of Beyond 1 Million Genomes⁴¹, GDI is establishing a federated, sustainable infrastructure based on community standards and Trusted Research Environment (TRE) principles.

As one of the key driver projects for EOSC-ENTRUST, GDI plays a central role in shaping and validating the Blueprint for federated access to sensitive data. Close alignment between the two initiatives ensures that the genomics-specific infrastructure developed by GDI is interoperable with the broader, cross-domain TRE framework defined by EOSC-ENTRUST. This collaboration supports convergence in architecture, governance, and access models, reducing fragmentation across European data infrastructures.

GDI also maintains strong synergies with the Genome of Europe⁴², launched in 2025, with a shared ambition to make large-scale genomic datasets accessible through the GDI federation. A formal Memorandum of Understanding underpins this collaboration.

During its first phase, GDI delivered key outputs, including the GDI Starter Kit for cross-border data access and demonstrations of federated analysis workflows using realistic synthetic datasets (e.g. colorectal cancer and COVID-19 use cases), which closely align with EOSC-ENTRUST Driver use cases. In the second half of the project, the focus is on consolidating these components, implementing final features, and preparing for long-term sustainability beyond the project's completion in October 2026, including links to future initiatives such as STORE-1+MG.

Consortium agreements can effectively formalise coordination and align operational efforts for storage and compute, but they often fall short in providing robust international frameworks for cross-border dispute resolution and federated services. This gap is directly relevant to the EOSC-ENTRUST blueprint, which aims to enable interoperable Trusted Research Environments across jurisdictions. Here, GDI can offer valuable input by leveraging the Genomic EDIC as a concrete legal and governance model, demonstrating how federated access to sensitive genomic data can be operationalised across borders and helping to strengthen the blueprint's approach to legal interoperability.

³⁹ Genomic Data Infrastructure, <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

⁴⁰ 1+ Million Genome initiative <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

⁴¹ B1MG Project, <https://b1mg-project.eu/>

⁴² Genome of Europe, <https://genomeofeurope.eu/>

4.2.4.2 DARE UK

Data Analytics and Research Environments UK (DARE UK) is a programme that aims to establish a safe and collaborative network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) where approved researchers can efficiently access and analyse sensitive data to advance research for public benefit. It is currently in Phase 2 (2024-2026) of a three-phase programme and publishes its programme outputs in the “DARE UK” community at Zenodo⁴³. Although the direct impact is for the UK, the outputs are investigating many of the same topics and similar challenges in EOSC-ENTRUST: i.e. federation, standardisation, user management. Key updates from the last 12 months are listed below.

SATRE v2.0

- The SATRE v2.0 “federation pillar” is in final draft⁴⁴. It is the culmination of multiple in-person and online collaborative events which have brought together TRE operators, TRE developers, information governance specialists, members of the public and researchers. SATRE v1 was one of the foundations of the EOSC-ENTRUST Architecture Blueprint, and subsequent work by the EOSC-ENTRUST consortium has in turn fed back into the drafting of the federation pillar.

K8TRE

- K8TRE is an open-source, vendor-neutral TRE being developed as part of the DARE UK TREvolution consortium. During the first year K8TRE has demonstrated the provisioning of secure analytical workspaces using Kubernetes on multiple platforms, including Microsoft Azure and Amazon Web Services public clouds, and K3s which can run on-premises. A reference TRE implementation can aid roll-out of federations across Europe through common technical solutions.

FRIDGE

- The FRIDGE project (Federated Research Infrastructure by Data Governance Extension) concluded recently in the DARE UK Early Adopter programme. FRIDGE’s focus was AI-driven research using sensitive data, and it successfully demonstrated the deployment of a SATRE- and UK NHS standards-compliant, cross-platform TRE on the UK’s AI Research Resource (AIRR) supercomputing systems at the Universities of Cambridge and Bristol. A notable output is a shared responsibility model connecting a “host” TRE (running at the Alan Turing Institute as part of FRIDGE) and remote “satellite” TREs at Bristol and Cambridge, deployed in both “FRIDGE tenancies” and K8TRE flavours. Of relevance to EOSC-ENTRUST when investigating Data Spaces and AI Factories in EHDS as many technical and governance issues are the same.

TETREs

- Launched fully in September 2025, the Test Environment for TREs is a collaboration of key UK TRE providers exploring the practicalities of federation at a technical level.

⁴³ DARE UK, https://zenodo.org/communities/dare_uk/records

⁴⁴ Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE), <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

It is a multi-cloud, distributed experimental infrastructure (including on-premises systems) and is focused on learning by doing. TETREs is deploying low-level, software-defined infrastructure in near-operational environments to understand the practicalities of configuring inter-TRE networks and supporting federated projects. It builds on key designs and software from the wider programme (SATRE, K8TRE, FRIDGE etc.). Its results will likely influence future TRE network implementations, including outside the UK.

HDR UK FED-A

- HDR UK Federated Analytics (FED-A) is an HDR UK workstream providing organisational and technical frameworks for TRE federation. It has developed the Federated Research Patterns Framework to consistently describe governance pathways towards different federation models (“weaves”) enabling secure cross-TRE collaboration and federated analysis workflows. This work contributes governance models relevant to the EOSC-ENTRUST Workflows prototype.

TREvolution / Five Safes TES

- The UKs only conference dedicated to Trusted Research Environments became a fully standalone multi-day conference in 2025. The conference focussed on federating TREs, and representatives of the EOSC-ENTRUST consortium were invited to share their work and experiences of federation in a real environment.

TRE Community Conference Sep 2025

- The UKs only conference dedicated to Trusted Research Environments became a fully standalone multi-day conference in 2025. The conference focused on federating TREs, and representatives of the EOSC-ENTRUST consortium were invited to share their work and experiences of federation in a real environment.

5. Results

5.1 Dissemination Activities

The second phase of the EOSC-ENTRUST Roadmap involved multiple dissemination activities presenting project results and gathering feedback from stakeholders, including the following:

- The second EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop (May 6-7, 2025)⁴⁵ was organized as an online meeting and focused on gathering input for the second version of the Blueprint and on aligning the project WPs.

⁴⁵ Kirschenmann, S., Winge, I., Sætrom, P., Kallberg, M., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., Lehvälaiho, H., van der Kant, A., Laine, H., Lényi, P., Liampotis, N., Gonzalo Jimenez, E., Fernández González, J. M., Couldridge, J., & Quinlan, P. (2025). 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15473397>

- The second EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation & Adoption Workshop (Sep 17-18, 2025)⁴⁶ was held in Bergen, Norway. The workshop presented and discussed recent developments from the Drivers, Providers, AAAI, and Workflow WPs and aligned these with the ongoing development of the Second year Blueprint. The workshop also discussed alignment with external developments within EHDS and DARE UK.
- The second EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint validation workshop (Dec 2-3, 2025) was organized as an online meeting and focused on reviewing the Second year Blueprint in the context of the Driver requirements and their ongoing work on developing Driver prototypes. The workshop provided input to the Drivers' gap analysis in the Driver validation report (see [Section 4.1.2](#)).
- The outreach workshop “Enabling Data Sovereignty through Trusted Research Environments in European Data Spaces” (Feb 25, 2026)⁴⁷ gathered external stakeholders online to discuss how TREs, and federations thereof, can support future Data Spaces and the EOSC Federation.
- EOSC-ENTRUST D14.3, the second-year blueprint for the interoperability and federation of TREs, was tabled at RDA Working Group on TREs for Sensitive and Confidential Data⁴⁸.

5.2 Revised Roadmap

[Figure 1](#) presents the EOSC-ENTRUST Roadmap as a phased implementation pathway for the delivery of the project's objectives related to the Blueprint and Interoperability Framework for Trusted Research Environments. The Roadmap is in line with previous versions^{49,50}, but has been updated to highlight the completed and remaining Blueprint deliverables. In Phase 1, the primary objective is to establish the conceptual and technical foundations by identifying blueprint requirements, mapping these to TRE capabilities, and producing the initial Roadmap and first machine-readable provider catalogue. The main

⁴⁶ Sætrum, P., Maccallum, P., van der Kant, A., Vihervalli, U., Kuba, M., Lehvälaiho, H., Cole, C., Kallberg, M., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., Winge, I., Kirschenmann, S., Couldridge, J., Fernández González, J. M., Codó, L., Iborra de Toledo, P., & Nagaraja Grellscheid, S. (2025). MS18 - Second EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation & Adoption Workshop. Second Evaluation and adoption Workshop, Bergen, Norway. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17160733>

⁴⁷ Orhanen, S., Jones, B., Chiarugi, D., Jefferson, E., Capella Gutierrez, S., & Matthiesen, M. (2026). Enabling Data Sovereignty through Trusted Research Environments in European Data Spaces – EOSC-ENTRUST workshop. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18954796>

⁴⁸ Baxter, R. Interoperability: the ENTRUST Blueprint. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/trusted-research-environments-for-sensitive-or-confidential-data-fairness-for-controlled-data-and-processes-wg/posts/?post=233493>

⁴⁹ Sætrum, P., & Negru, S. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.1 - Draft Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12703951>

⁵⁰ Sætrum, P., Kallberg, M., Lehvälaiho, H., Kirschenmann, S., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & van de Sanden, M. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D14.1 Updated Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15608124>

outcome of this phase is a shared baseline for subsequent development activities, with expected impact in terms of improved clarity, common terminology, and early alignment across stakeholders.

In Phase 2, the objective is to advance from foundation to creation and validation. This includes iterative refinement of the Roadmap, development and validation of key blueprint components, and delivery of the year two version of the Blueprint and Interoperability Framework together with the second edition of the provider catalogue. The expected outcome is a more mature and evidence-based interoperability framework, while the anticipated impact lies in strengthening practical readiness for interoperable TRE services and supporting broader uptake across the EOSC ecosystem.

In Phase 3, the objective is to consolidate project results and ensure maturity and continuity beyond earlier development cycles. This phase delivers the final Roadmap, the service catalogue for an interoperable TRE services network, the year three Blueprint, and associated training materials. The resulting outcome is a consolidated set of project assets supporting sustained implementation, with expected impact in terms of long-term interoperability, increased reusability of project results, and stronger capacity for adoption and continuity within the EOSC landscape.

EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and TRE Interoperability Roadmap (2024-2026)

Figure 1. EOSC-ENTRUST Roadmap showing the phased development, validation, and consolidation of blueprint and interoperability outcomes for TRE services within EOSC.

5.3 KPI status

When assessing the impact of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, it is essential to define appropriate Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that accurately capture the values most relevant to its successful implementation.

Key areas of measurement should include the extent to which the Blueprint is used for capability development within the TRE Providers Forum, as well as its adoption by multidisciplinary Drivers for strategy and delivery. In addition, KPIs should address the completeness of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, the maturity of the technologies developed to enable federated data access and use across multiple TREs, and the uptake of EOSC-ENTRUST’s policy-shaping efforts. [Table 1](#) summarizes the KPIs identified at the start of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, and their expected and current status. Based on the current status of the KPIs related to Drivers and Providers, the Blueprint is being adopted and used to an extent that is in line with or ahead of expectations.

Table 1. High-level Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to the measurement of the impact of the project indicated in the table below, as described in the project proposal. “Scale” lists the KPIs; “M12”, “M24”, and “M36” are the target values at project months 12, 24, and 36, matching the ends of Roadmap Phases 1, 2, and 3, respectively; “Assumptions & baseline” describes what is being measured; and “Status (M26)” lists the actual values at project month 26. Status values are based on the latest Driver and Provider reports.

Scale	M12	M24	M36	Assumptions & baseline	Status (M26)
KPI: Completeness of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint	20%	50%	80%	Number of accepted user requirements met	70%
KPI: Level of use of the Blueprint for capability development by TRE Providers Forum	1	6	15	Number of EOSC-ENTRUST providers using the blueprint for capability development.	11 (adopted or reviewing alignment between Blueprint and existing capabilities)
KPI: Maturity of technologies developed to enable federated data use & access across multiple TREs	0%	50%	80%	% of EOSC-ENTRUST solutions reaching TRL level 6	To be determined

KPI: Level of use of the Blueprint by multi-disciplinary Drivers for strategy & delivery	0	1	4	Number of EOSC-ENTRUST drivers using the blueprint for strategy and delivery	4
KPI: Uptake of EOSC-ENTRUST policy shaping efforts.	2	5	15	Number of national & EC policymakers reached with the Policy Briefs	To be determined

6. Discussion

The second year of the EOSC-ENTRUST project has seen the completion of the second phase in the Roadmap towards a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis – the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework (the Blueprint). This includes the second version of the Blueprint, with an updated architecture specification and initial versions of operating procedures, interface definitions, and template legal agreements, and accompanying second versions of the Training Package and TRE Catalogue. The phase also delivered the second version of AAI for TREs Blueprint and a working prototype of federated workflow-based analyses of genetic data. The Blueprint has been further validated by the Drivers in the context of their respective prototypes, which resulted in concrete recommendations for the final version of the Blueprint. Finally, work by the Providers have shown both interest in and actual adoption of the Blueprint, but also highlighted important barriers to such adoption.

In the third and final phase of the Roadmap, we will work to address gaps in the Blueprint identified during the Roadmap’s second phase. These include the specific Driver recommendations regarding architecture specifications, operating procedures, legal frameworks, and the roles and terminology used in the Blueprint.

7. Conclusions and Impact

The second year of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, corresponding to the second phase in the Roadmap, has seen the Blueprint develop into a first complete version, supported by validating prototypes from the Drivers, broader engagement from TRE providers outside the project, and further technical developments on AAI and workflows solutions. The current report has summarized this and relevant parallel developments within Europe. Based on this work, we have presented the final Blueprint roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST ([Figure 1](#)).

The summaries and final Roadmap presented here have informed our plans for the next steps in the Blueprint development (see below).

8. Next steps

As in the first phase of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, engagement across work packages and with external stakeholders has been critical for developing the second version of the Blueprint. We aim to continue this engagement in the final project phase, starting with the third EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop (May 5-6, 2026). The workshop is designed to gather and align the expectations of the Providers and Drivers towards the final version of the Blueprint, and identify and discuss obstacles for adopting the Blueprint from the perspective of TRE providers and use cases beyond the current EOSC-ENTRUST Drivers.

Following the Requirements and Capabilities Workshop, we will work to address the identified gaps in the Blueprint, focusing on the Driver recommendations. We aim to present a draft final version Blueprint during the third EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation and Adoption Workshop (to be held September 15-16, 2026).

In parallel with revising and extending the Blueprint, we will develop the third version of the TRE Provider Catalogue and continue developing training material for the Blueprint. The former will be developed in close collaboration with the Providers and their work in gathering data for the Provider Inventory.